

In the eyes of the students, COVID19 prevention efforts at Al Zahraa University

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Abstract:

Across sectional study was done to assess the COVID19 preventive strategies for students at Al-Zaraa University. A total of 182 undergraduate students in Health and Medical Technology college took part in this cross-sectional questionnaire-based study. Data from 182 students were collected and analyzed. Of the participant 57.7% were at the age of 19-20 yr., 152(83.5%) were residing at Karbala. 120(65.9%) of the students do not think that the university applied a preventive measure against COVID19. 95(52.2%) think that the university enforced students to wear masks inside the campus. Regarding social separation on campus, 162 (89 percent) believe it is not appropriate 156 (85.7%) and 116 (63.7%) of the participants, respectively, believed that there are no preventive measures against Corona in the campus cafeteria and university transportation. During the COVID19 pandemic, Al-Zahraa university' execution of prevention and control measures was found to be weak. Effective interventions are urgently needed to improve the rate at which social distance, environmental disinfection management, awareness campaigns, and medical care are implemented.

Keywords: COVID19, vaccine, prevention efforts, students, Al-Zahraa University, Iraq

Introduction:

Almost every country's higher education institution closed in the first half of 2020 because of the COVID-19 pandemic. University officials must now decide if and how to securely reintroduce students, workers, and professors to campus¹.

COVID19 has revolutionized the way people throughout the world study and teach.. Online webinars, such as WebEx and its counterparts, are currently being used to replace the traditional face-to-face method².

Technology has pervaded every aspect of our lives, and education is no different.. The latent purpose of maintaining social distance is likely to be one of the primary reasons for students to enroll in online courses during the present COVID-19 epidemic period³.

The World Health Organization has stated that the only way to slow the spread of the virus, control it, and reduce the number of cases and deaths caused by the pandemic is for people to adopt basic measures such as hand hygiene, alcohol gel use, cough etiquette, cleaning surfaces, avoiding agglomerations, and social distancing⁴.

The current coronavirus disease (COVID-19) pandemic has been linked to increased morbidity and mortality, affecting the lives of people all over the world. During the outbreak, human behavior and knowledge assessment are crucial in the overall attempt to contain the pandemic⁵.

Fear, worry, and tension are all natural reactions to perceived or real risks, uncertainty, and the unknown.. As a result, people's terror in the face of the COVID-19 epidemic is natural and understandable⁶.

Immunization programs and coverage are critical for protecting people of all ages from the debilitating and potentially life-threatening impacts of infectious illnesses⁷.

Protection from infectious disease is one of the most valuable benefits that any country can provide to its citizens. Vaccination is acknowledged as a preventive method that has contributed to lower mortality and morbidity rates⁸.

Nurses are facing issues regarding management, work environment, family cross-infection, self-infection risk, assault, emotional & physical drain, and psychological stress. Training to work in an isolation unit is essential, keeping in mind that they may suffer from psychological exhaustion⁹.

The rapid spread of the COVID-19 pandemic has caused widespread worry among health care professionals around the world. The most up-to-date information on the COVID-19 outbreak should be available to all healthcare professionals¹⁰.

Knowledge, attitudes, and practices (KAP) concerning COVID-19 determine a society's willingness to accept behavioral change initiatives from health authorities.¹¹.

Since a pandemic like COVID 19 has imposed forced lockdowns restraining customers all around the world, customers have demonstrated unusual behavior¹².

Methods:

At Al-Zahra University for Women, a total of 182 undergraduate students in Health and Medical Technology took part in this cross-sectional questionnaire-based study (x-ray department).. This Google Classroom were attended by 182 students. The questionnaire, resulting in a response rate of (100 percent). For the study, questionnaires were designed, and data from 182 students was collected and examined. Ethical approval was granted by the independent ethics committee of Al-Zahra University for women in Karbala-Iraq before to the research. The period of research and data collection was between Jan. 2021 and Sept. 2021. Protective measures such as wearing masks, taking students' temperature, sanitizing the classrooms, using soap and hand sanitizers in bathrooms, preventive measures in the university cafeteria and transportation, and air inflators available in university classrooms were among the items targeted at multiple areas of social and physical distancing. Questionnaires were distributed among the students using Google Classroom and were returned by the students after completing using the same way. These sites serve as official communication routes between schools and students. In addition, the academic class representative was active in personally disseminating the questionnaire link to students. The responses were retrieved as an excel file from the electronic form of a questionnaire (google-form) and imported into SPSS ver.23 to be analyzed and frequencies and percentages determined. The questionnaire is related to the COVID19 prevention efforts at Al Zahraa University for women in the form of multiple choices given to each participant. Questions on age, marital status, and current living situation were among the demographic data obtained in this study. This questionnaire is comprised of three tables with twenty-one questions. Statistical tests used frequency and rates.

Ethical consideration: The value of the study, as well as the freedom to share their information with the researcher while maintaining his privacy, are all mentioned in a consent message addressed to all recipients of the Questionnaire. Verbal consent to participate taken from each female, after informed her about the study objectives, time consumption, security of their answers, free to participate, and future benefits to their community.

Results:

As first-year students, 182 students in the x-ray department at Al-Zahra University for women participate in this study.

Table 1 shows the participants' demographic characteristics. Of the participant 57.7% were at the age of 19-20 yr., 34% were above 34 while 8.2% were above 21yr. 146(80.2%) are unmarried, 33(18.1%) are married and 3(1.6) are separated. The researcher found that 152(83.5%) were residing at Karbala while 30(16.5%) were outside Karbala. (Table1)

The family number ever diagnosed with COVID19 was 105(57.7%). We noticed that 49(26.9%) of the participant had a vaccine refusal history. While 77(42.3%) were refuse COVID19 vaccination. 22(12.1%) have a family member who died because of COVID19. Also, 122(67%) think that the COVID19 vaccine was not useful in the prevention of the disease. (Table2)

The researcher discovers that 120(65.9%) of the students do not think that the university applied a preventive measure against COVID19. In addition, in this study, we found that 95(52.2%) think that the university enforced students to wear masks inside the campus. Regarding social separation on campus, 162 (89 percent) believe it is not appropriate. Checking students' temperatures at the entrance to campus are one of the COVID19 prevention measures, yet only 60 (33%) of students thought it was accomplished. Most students 158 (86.8%) feel that the teaching staff was committed to COVID19 prevention. Does the university sterilize before allowing students to enter? The answer was Yes for 100 (54.9 %) students. In addition, 87 percent of participants (47.8%) feel that the institution would isolate suspected COVID19 patients. Soap and hand sanitizers were thought to be available in the university's bathrooms by 98 (53.8 %) students. 156 (85.7%) and 116 (63.7%) of the participants, respectively, believed that there are no preventive measures against Corona in the campus cafeteria and university transportation. Also, 66(36.3%) of the participants thought that air inflators were not available in university classrooms. Of the participants 63(34.6%), thought that the university did not conducting awareness campaigns to prevent corona. Is a corona vaccine or a nasal swab required for female students to enter the university? 162 participants (89 %) answer no. When asked if they supported mandatory attendance or remote e-learning, 107(58.8%) of the participants did not agree. (Table3)

Table 1. - The participants' demographic and health-related characteristics (N: %)

demographic Variables	N	%
Age (yr.)		
Below 19 yr.	15	8.3
19 yr.	51	28.2
20 yr.	53	29.3
21 Yr	31	17.1
Above 21 yr.	31	17.1
Marital status		
Married	33	18.2
Unmarried	145	80.1
Separated	3	1.7
Widow	0	0
Residency		
KARBALA	151	83.4
another governorate	30	16.6

Table 2: health-related characteristics Variables

health-related characteristics Variables		
Family member ever diagnosed with COVID-19	N	%
Yes	104	57.5
No	77	42.5
Any previous vaccine refusal history		
Yes	48	26.5
No	133	73.5
Do you accept the COVID19 vaccine?		
Accept	76	42
Refuse	105	58
Has a family member died from Corona?		
Yes	21	11.6
No	160	88.4

Table3: COVID19 prevention efforts at Al-Zahraa University for women in the eyes of the students

COVID19 prevention efforts at Al-Zahraa University for women In the eyes of the students	yes	%	no	%
Do you think that preventive measures is applicable in the university?	61	33.7	120	66.3
Do you think that wearing masks is applicable in the university?	94	51.9	87	48.1
Do you think that social distancing is enforced?	20	11	161	89
Does the university take the temperature of female students?	59	32.6	122	67.4
Is the teaching staff committed to the preventive measures against Corona?	158	86.8	24	13.2
Does the university sanitize before students enter the university?	100	45.9	82	45.1
Does the university isolate students with corona?	87	47.8	95	52.2
Are soap and hand sanitizers available in the bathrooms in university	98	53.8		46.2
Do you think that preventive measures against Corona in the university cafeteria are available?	26	14.3	158	85.7
Do you think that preventive measures against Corona in university transportation are available?	66	36.3	116	63.7
Are air inflators available in university classrooms?	116	63.7	66	36.3

Is the university conducting awareness campaigns to prevent corona?	119	65.4	63	34.6
Does the university impose a corona vaccine or nasal swab before female students enter the university?	20	11	162	89
Do you support compulsory attendance or distance e-learning?	57	41.2	107	58.8

Discussion:

Many school districts were forced to migrate to online learning because of school closures, which was a quick and intense process for many schools, students, instructors, and parents, demanding expertise and speed to prevent losing instructional time¹³. The researcher was unable to locate similar studies in the Middle East and other countries that evaluated COVID19 preventive measures used by the campus management.

In this study, 33.7% of the students think that preventive measures are applicable in the university.

According to the Shi study¹⁴, the average overall implementation rate of COVID-19 preventative and control measures was 80.0 % in a Chinese nursing home. It is a lot more than our research.

The replies were not shown strict COVID19 prevention measures in Al-Zahraa University regarding COVID19 prevention procedures. Teaching staff's commitment to the preventive measures and social distancing was (89 percent), preventive measures against Corona in the university cafeteria (85.7%) and wearing masks (85.7%). While 45.1 percent believe that the university management does not sanitize the campus before students arrive.

According to the Freeman study¹⁵, most have implemented masking (100%) and physical distance (99%) rules. De-densification of classrooms was another preventive strategy (61 percent). The findings of the Freeman study are like those of this research.

Conclusions:

During the COVID19 pandemic, Al-Zahraa university execution of prevention and control measures was found to be weak. At Al-Zahraa University, the safety of students and employees is a major priority. We believe that effective interventions are urgently needed to improve the rate at which social distance, environmental disinfection management, awareness campaigns, and medical care are implemented.

List of abbreviation:

COVID19= Coronavirus disease

KAP = Knowledge, attitudes, and practices

Ethics approval and consent to participate

This study was approved by the Human Research Ethics committee at Al-Zahraa university.

Consent for publication

Not applicable.

Availability of supporting data

Data are available at google class with the following link

<https://docs.google.com/forms/d/1cygCiyEqHscfwh-KUxLcjMSHpxkPx5azp2Afi4A0FEE/edit?usp=sharing>

Competing interests

The author declare that he has no competing interests.

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Authors' contributions

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